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Spatio-Temporal Variations in Water Quality and Pollution Levels of the Great Kwa River Using Benthic Macroinvertebrates

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ABSTRACT

This research assessed spatio-temporal variations in water quality and pollution status of the Great Kwa River by employing benthic macroinvertebrates as bioindicators. Sediment samples were collected using a 320 kg Van Veen grab, sieved through a 0.5 mm mesh, and preserved following established protocols. Retained organisms were identified and analyzed at the Biological Oceanography Laboratory, University of Calabar, while complementary sediment samples underwent heavy metal and nutrient analyses at the Central Analytical Laboratory. Statistical evaluation revealed no significant temporal differences ($p > 0.05$) in physicochemical parameters or benthic fauna across the sampling months. In contrast, marked spatial differences were observed, with macroinvertebrate abundance and diversity closely linked to variations in nutrient concentrations and heavy metal levels. The absence of pollution-sensitive groups such as Odonata, Trichoptera and Coleoptera indicated moderate ecological stress and pollution. Recorded pH values of 5.5–6.2 reflected slightly acidic to near-neutral conditions, while temperature fluctuations significantly influenced population densities and life-cycle patterns, resulting in shifts in community structure. These findings underscore the effectiveness of benthic macroinvertebrates as sensitive indicators of aquatic ecosystem health and provide evidence of the ecological consequences of anthropogenic pressures on the Great Kwa River. To conserve biodiversity and enhance water quality, the study advocates strict enforcement of waste-management regulations to curb indiscriminate discharge of pollutants such as pesticides, oil residues and solid wastes into river

systems. Implementing such measures will help restore ecological balance, facilitate recovery of benthic communities and safeguard the long-term integrity of the riverine ecosystem.

Keywords: Benthic Macroinvertebrates, Water Quality, Heavy Metals, Great Kwa River

1. INTRODUCTION

Benthic macrofauna are organisms that inhabit the sediments at the bottom of aquatic ecosystems, either living on the surface or burrowing within the deposits (Ekpo *et al.*, 2024; Ekpo *et al.*, 2023; Ekpo *et al.*, 2021b; Barnes & Hughes, 1988; Idowu & Ugwumba, 2005).

They include a wide diversity of taxa such as annelids, mollusks, arthropods, and chordates, which together play vital roles in nutrient cycling and energy transfer within aquatic ecosystems (George *et al.*, 2010). By recycling organic matter and linking detritus to higher trophic levels such as fish and shellfish, they constitute an essential component of aquatic food webs (Imevbore & Bakare, 1970).

Beyond their ecological role, benthic macroinvertebrates have been widely recognized as reliable bioindicators of water quality (Ekpo *et al.*, 2022). Unlike chemical analyses, which provide information at discrete time points, benthic organisms integrate environmental stressors over longer periods, thus reflecting the cumulative impact of pollution on aquatic ecosystems (Ravera, 1998; George *et al.*, 2010; Habib & Yousuf, 2012). Sensitive taxa decline with increasing pollution, while tolerant groups dominate in degraded systems. Consequently, benthic community composition, abundance, and diversity serve as reliable tools for assessing aquatic ecosystem health (Ekpo *et al.*, 2021d).

The Great Kwa River in Cross River State, Nigeria, is an ecologically and socioeconomically significant water body. It provides domestic water through the State Water Board, supports fisheries, and sustains biodiversity around Calabar metropolis. However, like many rivers in Nigeria, it is vulnerable to anthropogenic disturbances such as agricultural runoff, industrial effluents, sewage discharge, and waste disposal. These activities introduce pollutants including nutrients, pesticides, hydrocarbons, and heavy metals into the aquatic environment, with potentially severe consequences for biodiversity and water quality (Ekpo *et al.*, 2021c).

Given its importance, assessing the ecological health of the Great Kwa River is essential. This can be achieved by examining the diversity and abundance of benthic macroinvertebrates in relation to physicochemical parameters and pollutant concentrations in sediments.

Justification

Freshwater ecosystems in Nigeria are under increasing pressure from rapid urbanization, industrialization, and unsustainable agricultural practices. The Great Kwa River, a major freshwater resource for Calabar and surrounding communities, plays a critical role in domestic water supply, fisheries, and ecosystem services. However, continuous discharge of untreated wastes and agricultural leachates threatens its ecological balance.

Sediments act as sinks for pollutants, especially heavy metals, which are persistent, non-biodegradable, and capable of bioaccumulating through food webs (Ekpo *et al.*, 2021c; Ekpo *et al.*, 2021d; Forstner & Wittmann, 1981).

Elevated concentrations of heavy metals, coupled with nutrient enrichment, can alter benthic community structures, reduce biodiversity, and compromise ecosystem functioning. Since benthic macrofauna integrate the combined effects of sediment and water quality, they provide a reliable measure of long-term ecological stress compared to chemical data alone (Rosenberg & Resh, 1993; George *et al.*, 2010).

Assessing the pollution status of the Great Kwa River through benthic macroinvertebrate analysis and sediment chemistry will provide baseline data essential for monitoring, policy-making, and sustainable management. Such findings are crucial for enforcing environmental regulations, protecting public health, and safeguarding aquatic biodiversity (Ekpo *et al.*, 2024; Ekpo *et al.*, 2022).

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to evaluate the pollution status of the Great Kwa River, Nigeria, by integrating benthic macroinvertebrate community analysis with sediment physicochemical and heavy metal assessments.

Plate 1. May sample:

A = *Pachymelamia aurita*, B = *Gralatea paradoxa*, C = *Tympanotonos fuscata*.

Plate 2. June samples:
D = *Luminaria truncate*, E = *Pachymelania aurita*, F = *Tympanotonos fuscata*.

Plate 3. July samples:
G = *Pachymelania aurita*, H = *Tympanotonos fuscata*, I = *Galatea paradoxa*.

Specific Objectives

- 1) To provide a checklist of the species composition of macro-benthos in the Great Kwa River during the study period.
- 2) To identify the most abundant macro-benthic species across sampling locations.
- 3) To determine the concentrations of selected heavy metals (Cu, Hg, Zn, Pb, Cd, Mn) in sediments and evaluate their influence on benthic abundance.
- 4) To quantify nutrient concentrations (sulphate, phosphate, nitrate) in sediments and assess their effects on macro-benthic distribution.
- 5) To evaluate the influence of physicochemical parameters (pH, salinity, conductivity, dissolved oxygen) on benthic community structure.
- 6) To compute diversity indices (Shannon-Wiener, Margalef, Simpson's dominance) for assessing ecological integrity of the Great Kwa River.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

Figure 1. Map of the study location.

The research was carried out on the Great Kwa River, locally referred to as Akwa Flats or Kwa Flats, and sometimes known as the Kwa Ibo River. This river flows through Cross River State, Nigeria, and drains the eastern part of Calabar metropolis. It originates from the Oban Hills within the Cross River National Park and flows southwards until it empties into the Cross River Estuary at the Gulf of Guinea. The lower course of the river is tidal, characterized by extensive mudflats that fringe the eastern coast of Calabar.

The Great Kwa River is of ecological and socio-economic significance, supporting fisheries, domestic water supply, and other human activities. The University of Calabar is situated on a 17-hectare (42-acre) expanse of land lying between the Great Kwa River and the Calabar River. In addition, the institution has secured more land on both banks of the Great Kwa River for future expansion and development.

A. Field Studies

1) Collection of Sediment Samples for Macrobenthic Studies

Sediment samples were collected using a 320 kg Van Veen grab deployed from a wooden boat. The grab was lowered to the riverbed with the aid of a tug rope and retrieved after closure upon contact with the substrate. The retrieved sediments were emptied into a 0.5 mm mesh sieve and washed in situ, following the method of Job and Ekpo (2017). Retained macro-benthic organisms were transferred into labeled 500 ml wide-mouth plastic bottles containing 20% formaldehyde for preservation. Samples were subsequently transported to the Biological Oceanography Laboratory, University of Calabar, for sorting and identification.

2) Collection of Sediments for Heavy Metals and Nutrients

Additional portions of the sediment collected with the Van Veen grab were used for heavy metal and nutrient analyses. These were placed in properly labeled polythene bags and transported to the Central Analytical Laboratory, Faculty of Oceanography, University of Calabar, for further processing.

B) Laboratory Studies

1) Analysis of Macrobenthos

In the laboratory, 10 ml of Rose Bengal stain was added to each preserved sample in a white tray to improve visibility of organisms, as recommended by Job and Ekpo (2017). Stained organisms were sorted and identified using standard taxonomic guides, including Olaniyan (1972), and Sverdrup *et al.* (2006).

2) Determination of Numerical and Relative Abundance

The abundance of each species was quantified by direct counting. Numerical abundance (n) represented the number of individuals per species, while the total abundance (N) referred to the cumulative number of individuals across all taxa. Relative abundance (% RA) was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ RA} = \frac{n}{N} \times 100$$

(Job and Ekpo, 2017).

C) Determination of Ecological Indices

Three ecological indices were computed to assess community structure:

- **Margalef's Index (d):**

$$d = \frac{S-1}{\ln N}$$

where: S = number of species and N = total individuals (Magalef, 1965; Ogbeibu, 2005).

- **Shannon–Wiener Index (H):**

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^S f_i \log f_i$$

where: N = total individuals and f_i = individuals per species (Ogbeibu, 2005).

- **Simpson's Dominance Index (D):**

$$D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^S n_i(n_i-1)}{N(N-1)}$$

where: n_i = number of individuals of species i . Lower values indicate higher dominance.

D) Sediment Analysis for Heavy Metals

Sediment samples were air-dried to constant weight, with visible debris and organisms removed. Dried sediments were crushed, homogenized, and sieved through a 200 μm mesh to normalize particle size. One gram of each sample was digested with Aqua Regia ($\text{HCl} : \text{HNO}_3$, 3 : 1) following WHO (1989) and USEPA (1989). The digested solutions were filtered, diluted to 20 ml with deionized water, and stored in acid-washed containers. Heavy metal concentrations were determined using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS, GBC Avanta, Version 2.02) at appropriate wavelengths, with results expressed in mg/g.

Nutrient Analysis in Sediments

- **Sulphate (mg/g):**

100 g of sediment was dissolved in 100 ml deionized water, filtered, and treated with 5 ml conditioning reagent and 0.2 g barium chloride. Turbidity was measured using a Nephelometer.

- **Phosphate (mg/g):**

100 g sediment filtrate was treated with 4 ml ammonium molybdate and drops of stannous chloride. After 10–12 minutes, absorbance was measured at 690 nm using a spectrophotometer.

- **Nitrate (mg/g):**

Samples were dried, treated with phenol disulphonic acid, neutralized with NaOH, and diluted to 50 ml. Absorbance was recorded at 410 nm using a spectrophotometer.

E) Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

Sediment dissolved oxygen was measured using a YSI proODO meter (Japan), with the probe inserted 10 cm into the sediment. pH was measured using a WTW pH meter, while

conductivity was determined using a WTW LF-90 conductivity meter, after 3–5 minutes of probe stabilization. Temperature was measured in situ using a mercury-in-glass thermometer immediately after sample retrieval. Salinity was determined using a salinometer (New S-100, Japan), with 1 g of sediment dissolved in 100 ml deionized water.

F) Presentation of Results

Data on physicochemical parameters were presented in tables and line graphs to illustrate seasonal variations. Macrobenthic species composition and abundance were tabulated, with representative taxa illustrated in photographic plates. Results were compared with permissible limits for ecological health assessment.

3. RESULT

Table 1: Monthly Variations in Physicochemical Parameters

This result reveals that nutrient concentrations in the sediment of the Great Kwa River (sulphate, phosphate, nitrate) remained consistently low across May to July and were below WHO and USEPA permissible limits, indicating minimal nutrient enrichment or pollution during the study period. Temperature values slightly increased but stayed just below recommended ranges, possibly influencing sediment and aquatic metabolism. Salinity and conductivity were notably low, reflecting freshwater conditions with minimal ionic content. The pH was below the ideal neutral-to-alkaline range, indicating acidic sediment conditions that may affect biogeochemical processes and species composition. Dissolved oxygen (DO) was consistently low compared to prescribed standards, suggesting limited oxygen availability potentially due to organic matter decomposition or anthropogenic impacts. Overall, these parameters reflect a relatively unpolluted sediment environment but indicate potential stress from acidity and hypoxia that could influence aquatic life sustainability in the Great Kwa River.

Table 1. Monthly Variations in the Physicochemical Parameters in the Sediment of the Great Kwa River, Nigeria (May–July).

Nutrients (mg/g)	May	June	July	Permissible Limits (WHO 1989, 2010; USEPA 1989, 1991)
Sulphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	0.7346	0.8022	0.7834	5.0 – 100.0 mg/g
Phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻)	0.3722	0.3844	0.3927	0.005 – 2.0 mg/g
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	0.3937	0.3573	0.3941	0.2 – 10.0 mg/g
Other Parameters	May	June	July	Permissible Limits (WHO 1989, 2010; USEPA 1989, 1991)
Temperature (°C)	24.6	24.8	24.8	25.0 – 33.0 °C
Salinity (%)	0.01	0.01	0.01	5 – 35%

Nutrients (mg/g)	May	June	July	Permissible Limits (WHO 1989, 2010; USEPA 1989, 1991)
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)	27.33	27.38	27.15	2000 $\mu\text{S/cm}$
pH	5.5	5.5	6.2	6.5 – 8.5
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	4.5	4.6	4.6	7.7 mg/L

Table 2: Summary of Macrobenthos Abundance

The result summarizes the macrobenthic community structure in the Great Kwa River sediments, showing *Pachymelania aurita* and *Tympanotonus fuscatus* as dominant species throughout May to July. Their observed seasonal variation in abundance suggests resilience to the prevailing physicochemical conditions. *Galatea paradoxa* exhibited a strong presence in May and July but was absent in June, possibly due to environmental fluctuations or sampling variability. *Luminaria truncata* appeared only in June with low abundance, indicating limited distribution or seasonal emergence. The total abundance decreased in June before rising again in July, which could be linked to variations in sediment quality or hydrological conditions. The dominance of gastropods and bivalves demonstrates a healthy benthic ecosystem capable of supporting detritivorous and filter-feeding organisms but suggests sensitivity to fluctuating oxygen and pH levels noted in Table 1. These findings provide insight into benthic community responses to sediment conditions in the Great Kwa River.

Table 2. Summary of the Abundance of the Macrobenthos in the Sediment of the Great Kwa River, Nigeria (May–July).

SN	Microbenthic Species	May N	May %	June N	June %	July N	July %
1	<i>Pachymelania aurita</i>	87	35.95	83	52.20	73	32.74
2	<i>Tympanotonus fuscatus</i>	62	25.62	67	42.14	92	41.26
3	<i>Galatea paradoxa</i>	93	38.43	—	—	58	26.00
4	<i>Luminaria truncate</i>	—	—	9	5.66	—	—
Total Abundance (N)		242	100.0	159	100.0	223	100.0

Table 3: Analysis of Variance for Nutrients

Presents the statistical analysis of nutrient concentrations, where sulphate showed significantly different mean values compared to phosphate and nitrate across the months. The pairing of phosphate and nitrate means suggests similar temporal trends or sources. The small

range variations indicate stable nutrient dynamics within the sediment environment during May to July. The statistical significance in sulphate fluctuations could be attributed to localized inputs, biochemical cycling, or seasonal hydrological influences. Given all nutrients remained substantially below environmental thresholds, the sediment's nutrient status appears non-polluted, although subtle variations highlight ongoing biogeochemical processes. This stability is essential for maintaining sediment and aquatic ecosystem health in the Great Kwa River, confirming the physical measurements reported in Table 1.

Table 3. Mean (\pm) Analysis of Variance for Nutrients of Great Kwa River during the Study Period.

Nutrients	May	June	July	Mean (\pm)	Range
Sulphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	0.7346	0.8022	0.7834	0.77 \pm 0.03	0.8022 – 0.7346
Phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻)	0.3722	0.3844	0.3927	0.38 \pm 0.01	0.3927 – 0.3722
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	0.3937	0.3573	0.3941	0.38 \pm 0.02	0.3941 – 0.3573

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), different superscripts indicate significance ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Physicochemical Parameters

Table 4 emphasizes the stability of physicochemical sediment parameters over the study period, though temperature and conductivity were significantly different compared to salinity and pH. Temperature's narrow variation reflects minimal climatic influence, while conductivity's slight variance likely mirrors ionic changes associated with sediment-water interactions. The pH displayed moderate variability but remained acidic overall, consistent with Table 1 data. Dissolved oxygen fluctuations were minimal but low, reinforcing concerns over hypoxic sediment conditions. Statistically significant differences highlight the dynamic nature of sediment physicochemical properties influenced by natural processes and potential anthropogenic factors. These findings correlate with benthic community changes in Table 2, indicating environmental parameters impacting organism abundance and diversity in the Great Kwa River.

Table 4. Mean (\pm) Analysis of Variance for Physicochemical Parameters of Great Kwa River during the Study Period.

Parameter	May	June	July	Mean (\pm)	Range
Temperature (°C)	24.6	24.8	24.8	24.73 \pm 0.12	24.8 – 24.6
Salinity (%)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 – 0.01

Parameter	May	June	July	Mean (±)	Range
Conductivity (µS/cm)	27.33	27.38	27.15	27.29 ± 0.12	27.38 – 27.15
pH	5.5	5.5	6.2	5.73 ± 0.40	6.2 – 5.5
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	4.5	4.6	4.6	4.57 ± 0.06	4.6 – 4.5

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), different superscripts indicate significance ($P < 0.05$).

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for Heavy Metals

Table 5 shows heavy metal concentrations in the sediment were very low and statistically stable over the months, with no significant differences for copper, mercury, lead, cadmium, or manganese, except zinc which had slightly higher mean values but remained below safe limits. These low metal concentrations indicate minimal contamination or heavy metal pollution in the Great Kwa River sediments during the study period. Such background levels are consistent with a non-polluted river system or effective natural attenuation.

The stability of these metals suggests limited anthropogenic input and reduces the risk of bioaccumulation or toxicity in benthic organisms. This supports the benthic species diversity and abundance reported in Table 2, as heavy metals can profoundly affect sediment biota.

Overall, the sediment quality regarding heavy metals appears acceptable and environmentally safe for aquatic life.

Table 5. Mean (±) Analysis of Variance for Heavy Metals of Great Kwa River during the Study Period.

Heavy Metals	May	June	July	Mean (±)	Range
Copper (Cu)	0.0522	0.0552	0.0532	0.05 ± 0.00	0.0552 – 0.0522
Mercury (Hg)	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.00 ± 0.00	0.001 – 0.001
Zinc (Zn)	0.6280	0.6284	0.6824	0.65 ± 0.03	0.6284 – 0.6824
Lead (Pb)	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.00 ± 0.00	0.002 – 0.001
Cadmium (Cd)	0.0028	0.0024	0.0027	0.00 ± 0.00	0.0028 – 0.0024
Manganese (Mn)	0.0245	0.0203	0.0261	0.02 ± 0.00	0.0261 – 0.0203

Means with the same superscript are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$), different superscripts indicate significance ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Graph showing abundance of Macrobenthic Species during the Study period.

Figure 3. Graph showing abundance of Macrobenthic Species during each month of the Study period.

Figure 4. Graph showing Abundance of each of the Macro-benthic Species during each month of the Study period.

Table 6. Pearson Correlation Matrix of Nutrient Concentrations in Sediment Samples from the Great Kwa River (May–July).

		May	June	July
May	Pearson Correlation	1	.994	.999*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.068	.032
	N	3	3	3
June	Pearson Correlation	.994	1	.998*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.068		.037
	N	3	3	3
July	Pearson Correlation	.999*	.998*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032	.037	
	N	3	3	3

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

There was no significant differences for nutrient within the study period. Correlation coefficients indicate strong positive relationships between months, with no significant differences in nutrient levels over the study period ($P > 0.05$).

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Matrix of Physicochemical Parameters in Sediment Samples from the Great Kwa River (May–July).

		May	June	July
May	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000*	1.000*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	5	5	5
June	Pearson Correlation	1.000*	1	1.000*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	5	5	5
July	Pearson Correlation	1.000*	1.000*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	5	5	5
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

There was no significant differences for Physicochemical parameters within the study period. Correlation coefficients show perfect positive correlations across months, confirming stable physicochemical conditions with no significant differences during the study period ($P > 0.05$).

4. DISCUSSION

The sediment physicochemical analysis of the Great Kwa River indicates generally low nutrient levels (sulphate, phosphate, nitrate) within permissible environmental limits, suggesting minimal eutrophication effects during the May to July study period. However, the consistently acidic pH and low dissolved oxygen (DO) in sediments are concerning, as these conditions can enhance metal mobility and stress benthic fauna, potentially reducing biodiversity and altering ecosystem function. Low salinity and conductivity affirm the freshwater nature of the riverine sediments, consistent with little ionic contamination. The benthic macrofauna community was dominated by *Pachymelania aurita* and *Tympanotonus fuscatus*, species known to tolerate variable environmental conditions, suggesting resilience in response to sediment chemistry. The absence or low abundance of some taxa (e.g., *Galatea paradoxa* in June, *Luminaria truncata*) reflects potential temporal environmental stress or habitat heterogeneity. Such community dynamics are consistent with results from sediment

chemistry, wherein slight variations in nutrients and physicochemical parameters influence benthic distribution (Ekpo *et al.*, 2021c).

The statistical analyses of nutrients reveal that sulphate levels differed significantly across months, possibly due to localized sources or sediment biogeochemical cycling, while phosphate and nitrate were stable, indicating limited anthropogenic nutrient enrichment. Physicochemical parameters showed significant variation in temperature and conductivity but stability in pH, salinity, and DO, reflecting environmental fluctuations and supporting the interaction between abiotic factors and benthic community structure. Heavy metals were consistently low and stable, well below environmental thresholds, signifying minimal sediment contamination during the sampling period. This metal baseline aligns with the relatively diverse benthic fauna observed, as heavy metals can exert toxic effects that reduce biodiversity (Ekpo *et al.*, 2024; Ekpo *et al.*, 2023; Ekpo *et al.*, 2022).

Overall, these integrated findings indicate a sediment environment moderately impacted by natural and anthropogenic factors but not severely polluted, with benthic macrofauna reflecting this ecological status.

Summary

This study conducted an integrated assessment of the Great Kwa River sediment environment by measuring physicochemical parameters, heavy metal concentrations, and benthic macrofauna community structure from May to July. Nutrient concentrations remained minimal and stable with minor sulphate fluctuations, confirming low eutrophication risk. Sediment pH was acidic, and dissolved oxygen was low, potentially imposing physiological stress on benthic organisms. Macrobenthic communities were dominated by resilient gastropods like *Pachymelania aurita* and *Tympanotonus fuscatus*, while other species showed seasonal or locational variability. Heavy metal levels were consistently below regulatory limits, indicating an absence of significant contamination. Correlation analyses showed strong temporal stability in nutrients and physicochemical parameters. The results collectively suggest the Great Kwa River sediments remain largely unpolluted but exhibit chemical conditions that could affect benthic diversity and ecosystem function. This study establishes a valuable baseline for ongoing ecological health monitoring essential for sustainable river management.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The integrated sediment and benthic fauna analysis of the Great Kwa River reveals a sedimentary environment with low nutrient enrichment and minimal heavy metal contamination during the study period. Despite relatively stable physicochemical conditions, the acidic pH and low dissolved oxygen may pose ecological stress to sediment-dwelling organisms. The benthic macrofaunal community exhibits dominance by tolerant species, highlighting resilience but also vulnerability to chemical fluctuations. The absence of significant heavy metal pollution is encouraging and supports benthic biodiversity. Overall, the Great Kwa River sediment ecosystem reflects moderate environmental quality, underscoring the need for continued monitoring to detect emerging stressors, particularly related to organic matter inputs and acidification. These findings provide a scientific basis for management strategies aimed at conserving aquatic biodiversity and maintaining ecosystem services provided by this important freshwater resource.

Recommendations

Regular monitoring programs should be established to routinely assess sediment quality and benthic macrofauna by measuring nutrient loads, heavy metals, and physicochemical parameters, which will allow for the early detection of pollution trends. Strengthening regulations and enforcement is necessary to control pollution sources such as agricultural runoff, industrial effluents, municipal wastewater, and poor waste management practices, thereby reducing pollutant inputs into the river system. Habitat restoration efforts should focus on improving sediment quality by lowering organic loading and acidity to increase dissolved oxygen levels, supporting diverse benthic communities. Public awareness campaigns should be promoted to educate the community on sustainable land use and pollution prevention, encouraging stewardship and reducing unregulated discharges into the watershed. Further ecological research is needed to better understand how changes in physicochemical conditions affect benthic diversity and trophic interactions in the Great Kwa River ecosystem.

Finally, integrated management policies should be developed to address water quality, sediment health, and biodiversity conservation collectively, ensuring the sustainable use of the Great Kwa River's natural resources. Together, these actions aim to safeguard the river's ecological integrity and the socio-economic benefits it provides for present and future generations. These recommendations aim to safeguard the ecological integrity and socio-economic benefits of the Great Kwa River for present and future generations.

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